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ABSTRACT

Background: Leadership and culture shape each other. The culture and civilization of any nation help a leader to understand the needs of his followers and lead them in a better way. The prevalent leadership practices of a particular nation make an impression on the ethos of the country. This two-fold relationship between culture and leadership has been well established through cross-cultural management studies. Leadership styles differ significantly across nations. This review highlights the dominant leadership styles practiced by the managers in India and worldwide. The recent development of Indian models of leadership has also been discussed briefly to facilitate the understanding of leadership practices in India. This review identified a research gap in the study of leadership styles from indigenous perspectives. There is a need for more extensive research on leadership behaviour and practices considering cultural influences on human life. Practicing leadership styles with an understanding of people and their cultural ethos will make the leader more effective. This will further lead to a more effective and prosperous organization.

Keyword: Leadership, Cross-Cultural Management, Indian Models of Leadership, Organizational Effectiveness

Introduction:

The task of the leader is to get their people from where they are to where have not been.

-Henry Kissinger

Leadership has always been a complex and vital phenomenon. Its profound influence on human life is visible from the very beginning of civilization to the modern world. However, leadership is an inevitable concept in life today. As a political leader put his country in certain direction through his actions, equally the leading behaviour and strategies of a manager or leader in workplace influences the different dimensions of an employees' life. In simple words, leadership styles can be seen as a central construct to impact various factors in workplace related to employee and the organization. Miriam Grace (2003) in his work "Origins of Leadership: The Etymology of Leadership" presented a detailed inquiry about the inception of the word leadership. Major indications are - 'leadership' has its core in the word 'lead' which is the causal form of 'lithan' meaning to travel. In 1908, the new English dictionary introduced the psychological meaning of leadership as "the ability to lead". Peter Drucker (1970), widely known as father of management defined leadership in words, "Leadership is the lifting of man's visions to

higher sights, the raising of a man's performance to a higher standard, the building of a man's personality beyond its normal limitations." A more recent definition of leadership is given by Aykut et al. (2008), "Leadership is a communication process of influencing and directing people to commit to and achieve a shared goal voluntarily, in a given situation".

Leadership can be understood as sum total of handful fundamental peculiarities which constitutes it. In simple words leadership is a process of putting people in more positive and forward direction in the way of achieving their goals; with changing the things, transforming and creating new visions about situations, and revealing the hidden dimensions of their personalities.

A 'Style' is a pattern of behaviour associated with the specific role of the leader or the manager in the organization. Casimir (2001) defined leadership style as a pattern of emphases, indexed by the frequency or intensity of specific leadership behaviours or attitudes, which a leader places on the different leadership functions. Different studies and scholars identified several leadership styles, in which prominent ones are authoritarian, democratic, bureaucratic, transformational and transactional styles. A brief description is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. The Classic Styles of Leadership

Studies	Leadership styles	Description
Lewin at el. (1939)	Authoritarian	Leaders or authority figures keeps all power in their hands. Policies and all decisions are made by leaders without including members or group suggestions. Every step related to tasks also dictated by leaders.
	Democratic	The Leader encourages group activities. Decisions are taken based on group discussions and the leader assists all the processes very carefully. The leader provides many suggestions and alternatives from performing a task to solving decision-related problems.
	Laissez-faire	A leader provides very little or almost no guidance for decision making. Individuals or groups are free to make decisions on their own. This style works especially when participants are highly qualified and trained in a particular task.
Weber (1947)	Bureaucratic	Bureaucratic style refers to leadership which well defines the hierarchy and the division of labour within a highly structured organization based on formal rules and regulations. Additionally, rules and decisions are completely made and imposed by a higher level of authority.
	Charismatic	According to Weber "the term charisma will be applied to a certain quality of an individual personality by virtue of which he is set apart from ordinary men and treated as endowed with supernatural, superhuman, or at least specifically exceptional powers or qualities"
Downton (1973)	Transformational	Burns (1978) defined Transformational leadership as "leaders and followers help each other to advance to a higher level of morale and motivation."
	Transactional	Downton (1973) defined transactional leadership as "a process of exchange that is analogous to contractual relations in economic life [and] contingent on the good faith of the participants".

Culture and Leadership:

It is well said by Edgar Schein (2004), that culture and leadership are two sides of the same coin. This metaphor is for a better understanding of how these two concepts are intertwined with each other. Hence, it becomes necessary to consider the role of culture as a crucial aspect of the effectiveness of leadership. A leader must be aware of and discern the thoughts and necessities of the followers. As Rubenstein (2003) reviewed "Culture is a dynamic, symbolically based learned system. It forms the mechanism through which people

construct and intact meaning." Thus, not only leaders but culture also has an impact on how followers comprehend the leader's behaviour. In other words, the values, believes, and symbolic interpretations of the leader as well as the follower are decided mostly by the culture.

Cross-Cultural Studies of Leadership Styles

Taleghani et al. (2010), extensively discussed the leaders' attributes and cultural influences on organizational behaviour and what followers expect from their leader depend on the cultural values in which they grew up. The studies suggest that leaders from Japan tend to be more people oriented in their approach rather than task oriented. Leaders expect complete loyalty from their follower and maintain good interpersonal relationships among followers. Opposite of this, Chinese leaders support hierarchical structure and centralized decision-making system with less or almost no participation of followers. American CEOs tend to use directive, participative, empowering and charismatic styles. Management Research Group (MRG) had compared leadership behaviours of almost 4,000 individuals in eight European countries including Belgium, Denmark, France, Germany, the Republic of Ireland, the Netherlands, Sweden and United Kingdom. Results showed three common factors across all these nations - Expertise, Competitiveness, and Setting standards of Excellence. A comparative perspective of western leadership practices and cultural essence found visibly present in Arab Countries. Many Arab managers behave like father figure and this behaviour led to an authoritative style of management - mostly could be seen in large organizations.

Harvard Business Review published an article entitled "What Leadership Looks like in Different Cultures" penned by Premuzic, T. C. and Sanger, M. (May 06, 2016). A directly quoted paragraph from that article is as follows -

"...the full recipe of successful leadership, the lay beliefs about the qualities that individuals need to display to be considered leaders. Depending on the cultural context, your typical style and behavioural tendencies may be an asset or a weakness. In other words, good leadership is largely personality in right

place".

A research project named Global Leadership and Organizational Behavior Effectiveness (GLOBE) initiated and funded by Robert J. House (1991). This research project included sixty-two participating countries and studied leadership, organizational practices and national culture. Based on this study, leadership was defined as "the ability of an individual to influence, motivate and enable others to contribute towards the effective and success of the organizations of which they are members" (House et al., 2004). Authors enlisted some characteristics for a leadership style to be successfully implemented in Indian organizations: integrity, being organized, an action orientation, being a self-starter, charismatic, and a collective orientation; with being a problem solver, a visionary, entrepreneurial, and inspirational.

There are some empirical evidences indicating differences in leadership styles practiced in Indian organizations and organizations in other countries. A study named 'A Comparative Analysis of Leadership styles in New Zealand and India' done by Gandhi (2016) indicated that India has a more authoritative approach where New Zealand maintains a highly democratic stance. Carroll & Patterson, (2014) examined the cross-cultural differences in servant leadership across India and United States. Study consisted a total sample of 466 respondents from Information-Technology (IT) industry of both countries. No significant difference has been found in both the cultures (India and USA) for the perception of servant leadership except for the characteristics of the vision. V. C. Sharma et al. (2016) analysed the transformational leadership behaviours of top level Indian and USA business leaders such as President, Vice-President, CEO or Managing Director of a large business organizations. Leadership behaviours has been measured by using Leadership Practice Inventory (LPI) developed by Kouzes & Posner (2003). Comparison was based on 5

dimensions of LPI; Modelling the way (MW), Inspiring a Shared Vision (ISV), Challenging the Process (CP), Enabling Others to Act (EOA) and Encouraging the Heart (EH). The Indian and USA leaders were significantly differed in practicing Modelling the way (MW) and Inspiring shared vision (ISV).

Researchers have studied various leadership styles practiced in Indian organizations. V. D. Puranik (2012) had completed the Ph.D. thesis titled "An analytical study of leadership styles in diverse organizations". In this study, 146 middle-level managers from IT (information technology), MNCs (multinational corporations), NGOs (Non-government organizations), private and public sectors; and their 242 respective subordinates had been included. This investigation helps to understand the personality and motivation traits of managers from varied organizations and different leadership styles practiced by them along with the expectations of their subordinates about the leadership behaviour. It showed that the selling style- high task and high relationship- was a highly adopted style as compared to other styles by the managers of each organization; highly practiced (74.1%) by IT sector managers and lowest (48.5%) among the private sector managers. Selling style was also the most expected style among subordinates across all organizations. Further, this study added that emotional intelligence had been found high in NGO leaders and low in public sector managers.

Qualitative research was done by B.S. Joshi (2015) to understand the leadership styles accepted by the top and middle-level managers from hotels and hospitals. Bureaucratic (including the meanings and terminologies of participative, collaborative, people-oriented styles, etc) style was highly adopted among the top and middle-level managers from both organizations. The second most exhibited style was autocratic (dictatorial) by the middle-level managers from both organizations as well as moderately showed

by top management.

These are some empirical researches done in India to explore the leadership styles practices by Indian managers. A brief review of theories and models of leadership developed by the Indian researchers would be helpful in the understanding of leadership from Indian perspective.

Historical Roots and Recent Developments in Leadership in India

The concept of management is like an old tree rooted from very ancient time and has grown up with the civilizations of the world. India is one of the oldest civilizations in the world. Indian scriptures are the major sources of several theoretical foundations in almost every aspect of life. These Indian scriptures are assumed to be several thousands of years old. Vedas, Puranas, Upanishads, Smritis, Gita, Ramayana and Mahabharata are some of the main ancient texts providing conceptual foundations about Indian management thoughts and concepts. Indian management comprise the ethos, believes and intellect of ancient India. From fundamentals of management to producing eminent leaders; such as Chanakya, Buddha, Swami Vivekanand and Ghandi etc., were observed in every stage of Indian history- Mauryan rule, Gupta rule, the Mughal period to British empire. Besides the Indian scriptures, work done by great spiritual leaders and saints, can be followed. Swami Vivekanand in his articles entitled, 'Work and its secret' and 'Karma-yoga' talked about the importance of work and the purification of mind which can be achieved by selfless work and devotion. These types of thoughts provide a great insight of Indian wisdom.

Many other spiritual thinkers such as Shankara, Raman Maharshi, Sir Aurobindo, Ravindra Nath Tagore and Mahatma Gandhi expressed their thoughts in various aspects of life which influenced many spiritual gurus, management and social thoughts in modern times. In recent decades numerous authors

tried to comprise the thoughts and insights of ancient Indian scriptures (such as -Vedas, Puranas, Upanishads, Bhagwad Gita, Mahabharata, Arthashastra etc.) into Indian models and theories of leadership. Some of these models developed by Indian authors has been listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Indian Model of Leadership

Model of leadership	Major characteristics of the Model	Study
Nurturant-Task (NT) Leadership	NT leader cares for subordinates and their well-being, helps them in their personal and family matters, subordinated can depend on him for guidance & direction.	Sinha (1980)
OCTAPACE Model	For an effective organization these values must be imbibed in organizational culture: Openness, Confrontation, Trust, Authenticity, Proactive, Autonomy, Collaboration and Experimentation.	Pareek (1981)
PI (Pioneering Innovative) Management	Management policy framework should be committed to Pioneering novel products, services and technologies and an innovative, risk-taking, and experimental approach.	Khandwalla (1983)
Karta Model	Rooted from the joint family system (<i>Kutumbh</i>) of India and the head of family <i>Karta</i> . Karta leader possess the quality of a father-figure and looks his organization as a big extended family and subordinates as a family member.	Singh & Bhandarker (1990)
HOPE & OSHA Model	Enhancing management qualities through values HOPE (Higher Order Purpose for Existence). OSHA is a holistic development model O stands for oneness with nature, S- Spirituality, H- Humanity, and A- Animality.	Subhash Sharma (1995)
Mother Leadership	A model based on 'mother' metaphor, adopting the qualities for workplace from a role of mother. A model emphasizing towards the holistic development of the leader.	Banerjee (1998)
Workshop Model	Considering work as worship is a basic idea from ancient Indian sayings. The fundamental insight is if one assumes his work as virtuous as worship and devote himself to his work purely then drastic changes in the quality of work can be seen.	Chaterjee (1998)
Multifaceted Leadership Model from Ramayana	Based on the characteristics of Lord Rama which can be identified throughout the life journey. Some are listed by author as- detachment from ongoing experiences, righteousness, mentoring, resilience, nurturant, motivated, effective communication skill, charismatic, self-realized and enlightened leader.	Prema Ramachandran (2016)
Rajarshi Model (a framework of transcendental leadership)	Proactive change agent, Openness with Inclusion, Value-based decision making, Man-Machine entanglement, and leading towards the Ardhnarishwar are some characteristics of transcendental or timeless leader drawn from the <i>Rajarshi</i> concept.	Swami Bodhananda (2019)

The table above presents a very brief introduction of Indian models of leadership. Along with the indigenous theory and models of leadership, Indian leaders has been globally recognized for their leadership skills. In modern India portraits of prominent leaders can be painted as Business tycoons Mukesh Ambani, Ratan Tata, Anand Mahindra, and Laxmi Mittal; Yog Guru Baba Ramdev, and Honourable Prime Minister Sri Narendra Modi. These are some prominent names of leaders in India that emerged in recent decades. In a global scenario, we can name many top CEOs of Indian origin in the world as Leena Nair- CEO, Chanel; Sundar Pichai - CEO, Google LLC & Alphabet; Satya Nadella - CEO, Microsoft; Shantanu Narayen - CEO, Adobe Inc.; Jayshree Ullal - CEO, Arista Networks and so on.

Hindustan Unilever's Former CEO Manvinder Singh Banga once said "Indian leaders ... have been trained or groomed in extremely fluid, dynamic, uncertain environments. [Thus, they have] a much greater ability to cope with uncertainty, they don't get disturbed by uncertain events, they keep an even keel... They also tend to be more creative as a result, because they have to face these sorts of untoward situations almost on a daily basis." (Harvard Business Review, 2010)

Somehow these lines are a brief description of Indian leaders' life and the experiences they face over across the life interval. Because India has always been such an extraordinary representation of a unique culture that emerged as a result of the mixture of different societies through ages. Apart from that, Indian societies have so many rituals, traditions, and values teaching a person to grow old realizing his or her maximum potential. Such surroundings make an individual's life full of experiences with plenty of life-lessons. Leaders in India go through with massive rigorous experience in their daily lives that makes them

more receptive to various challenges with great coping skills for any kind of situation.

Conclusion

Leadership is an elementary phenomenon that considerably determines the success or failure of any organization. As discussed earlier, Leadership styles can be different across the culture. House in 1991 carried out a research project named 'GLOBE' (Global Leadership and Organizational behavior Effectiveness) that was based on the idea that leadership practices differ and are greatly influenced by the national Culture of the country. These findings suggest the study of leadership according to cultural values will present a different picture of leadership with a broader understanding.

According to the Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior (2020), national culture plays a critical role in the effectiveness of leadership behaviour (Takeuchi, Wang & Farh, 2020). Numerous researches in India which assessed the leadership styles from a western point of view, indicated the relationship of leadership styles with various job behaviours and organizational outcomes (Giri & Santra, 2008; Malik & Ansari, 2014; Pradhan & Pradhan, 2015; Shiva & Suar, 2011). These researches measure leadership style with western perspective. Again, some important researches conducted to study the leadership styles of Indian managers concerning cultural framework (Mohan, A. C. 2003; Nayak & Mishra, 2005; Suar et al., 2006). A review of the literature shows a lack of detailed conceptual understanding of Leadership styles in India with a culture-specific framework.

This study identifies the need to explore the leadership style from the Indian Perspective for a detailed understanding of the nature of leadership in India. This will assist in understanding leadership styles of Indian managers from indigenous perspective. Studying leadership styles with indigenous perspective

will help to understand the followers' need in relation to the leadership styles of Indian managers. It will provide a better insight to various issues regarding the implementation of leadership so that effectiveness of the organization could be maximized. This study also fulfils the research gap for better understanding of leadership styles from Indian perspective.

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